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OVERVIEW OF MASS PRODUCTION RANGE EXTENDER HYBRID ELECTRIC VEHICLES.

Keldiyarova Malika Shuhrat qizi^{1*}, Ruzimov Sanjarbek Komilovich^{2,3}

¹ Toshkent davlat transport universiteti tayanch doktoranti,

² Toshkent shahridagi Turin politexnika universiteti dotsenti,

³ Toshkent Kimyo xalqaro universiteti.

Abstract. Transportation sector is one of the main consumers of fossil fuels and therefore publicly recognized cause of climate change. In last decades, to reduce fuel consumption and emissions in vehicles, battery electric vehicles (BEV) and hybrid electric vehicles (HEV) are used. Due to range limitation and high cost of batteries, BEVs cannot be a widespread solution to the problem especially in the areas with limited availability of charging infrastructure. Range extender hybrid electric vehicles (REX HEV) uses technology that can be considered as intermediate solution. BEVs with range extender technology have onboard charging feature using an Internal Combustion Engine (ICE) which generates energy to extend the driving range and/or charge the battery. The aim of this study is to analyze and compare technical parameters of several REX HEVs available on the market.

Key words. Range extender, engine, battery, electric motor, HEV, BEV.

Introduction. Improvements on fuel economy and reduction of emissions is one of appropriate solutions on decreasing the influence of transport on global climate change [1]. Both BEVs and HEVs have their strong and weak sides which mainly regards to their driving range and fuel consumption. Advantages of using BEVs are having zero emissions and no fossil fuel dependency, on the other hand, lack of charging infrastructure and driving range limitations are considered as the main disadvantages. Extending the driving range of BEVs by adding ICE coupled with a generator set as a range extender can be a potential way in increasing the driving range. The drivetrain of HEVs have three architectures including series, parallel and series-parallel (combined) [2]. The series configuration of REX HEVs has advantages such as simple configuration and relatively less complex energy management system due to decoupling the electric motor and ICE. There are currently some vehicles on the market that use REX concept such as Chevrolet Volt, Fisker Karma, BMWi3, and Cadillac ELR [2]. The drivetrain technology of REX HEVs is based on series architecture, where an electric motor (EM) is only responsible for driving the wheels, while ICE is used to extend the driving range (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Series HEV architecture

Series hybrid electric vehicles have several advantages listed below [2]:

- ICE is decoupled from driving wheels so that it can kinematically be operated at its most optimum point;
- An EM is only driving source therefore it is low costly with the most simplified configuration.
- Series HEVs are less complex in both couplings and control algorithms. This leads to easier development and production of the vehicles compared to other architectures.

Methodology

Technical specifications of three different range extender hybrid electric vehicles which are in mass production are analyzed in this study.

Analyzing component size of different REX HEVs

The series as well as REX HEVs have simpler construction compared to other HEV configurations. The powertrain of REX HEV is the same with series hybrid electrical vehicle, also referred as electrical coupling. The main components of Rex HEVs are an internal combustion engine coupled with generator [3], battery pack and an electric traction motor. Typically, the engine has smaller size compared that in conventional drivetrain and has two or three cylinders. Different types of engines such as rotary [4], gas turbine, fuel cells, and Stirling engines can be used to drive the generator. It is common that the operation of the engine is restricted to a few operating points, since the its rotational speed is kinematically decoupled from the vehicle speed.

1. BMW i3 2014 REX HEV

The BMW i3 was manufactured between 2013 to 2021 [5]. It has to variants, pure BEV and REX HEV. To extend the driving range, an optional range extender ICE was used together with generator. BMW i3 2014 consists of a 0.65L in-line 2-cylinder gasoline ICE with a 26.6kW generator, 125kW permanent magnet synchronous AC motor, and 18.8kWh lithium-ion battery [6]. The controller is based on rule-based strategy. According to these rules the charge depleting mode (CD) changes to charge sustaining mode (CS) when the battery state of charge drops below 16% [6]. In CD mode, i.e. when the battery is sufficiently charged, the vehicle operates only in pure EV mode. When ICE starts to operate, three range of speed and two range of torque (overall six operating points) can be used according to level of battery charge and required driving torque.

2. Chevrolet Volt 2016

The Chevrolet Volt 2016 uses REX HEV powertrain introduced into the market in 2016 [7]. The Chevrolet Volt 2016 uses two motor generators in the powertrain. Kim, N.et.al [8] analyzed the performance of the Chevrolet Volt 2016 model based on Argonne's Advanced Powertrain Research Facility (APRF) test data in different operating conditions. Also, in this

vehicle, the rule-based control strategy. The threshold of battery SOC to switch from CD to CS is 16.5%. As Chevrolet Volt 2016 has two EMs more operation modes can be obtained such as two pure EV and three REX HEV modes. These modes are obtained by engaging or disengaging the clutches and depending on vehicle speed and battery SOC.

3. Fisker Karma 2012

Fisker Karma is a REX electric sport sedan vehicle which was produced by Fisker Automotive in 2012 [9]. The powertrain consists of two 120 kW electric motors powered by a 20.1kWh lithium ion battery. The ICE is 191 kW, 2 L four-cylinder gasoline engine driving the generator. In case of depleted battery, the ICE powers the generator that supplies electricity to the drive motors. The vehicle has three driving modes [10]: only battery traction, engine assist and regenerative braking during the down-hilling.

Results and discussion

In terms of ICE, the BMW i3 REX has engine almost twice smaller than Chevrolet Volt has (see Figure 2). While the Volt has a shorter EPA electric range than the i3 REX, 85 km compared to 115 km, respectively. The extended range due to ICE assist is about 590 km, compared to the BMW's 125 km [11]. As Karma is primarily sport car, it has big engine size with good dynamic performance having 201 km/h top speed and smaller acceleration time [11] compared to others.

Conclusions and future work

This paper compared three different range extender hybrid electric vehicles according to component sizes and performances. It founds that mainly rule-based control strategy is used in REX HEVs. Furthermore, there is not clear indication show the REX HEV powertrain is sized. Therefore, in the future, it would be reasonable to address component size issues to achieve minimal fuel consumption.

Figure 2. The main component sizes of BMW i3 REX, Chevrolet Volt and Fisker Karma

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